

The Geothermal Village Project (GV1)
Supported by the LEAP-RE Research Programme
Launched by the EU in Partnership with the AU

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ABSTRACT

The Research and Development (R&D) project called “Geothermal Village 1” (GV1) was granted 950.000 Euros for a 3 year period by the EU research programme called LEAP-RE . This project aims at developing renewable energy solutions for Africa. The objective of GV1 is to introduce geothermal-based stand-alone electric and thermal energy systems to African communities located off -grid, providing template case-studies on adapting the energy systems to community needs. We will demonstrate this by choosing sites with different thermal and socio-economic characteristics and developing for each site a suitable energy plan. We aim to keep the technology level appropriate to local operation, maintenance and replication, which furthers the long-term objective of capacity development , economic and social welfare, and encourage young educated people to stay on their homeland. Finally, these systems will empower women and girls by: (i) supplying fresh water and (ii) clean cooking solutions by supplanting oil and firewood. This in turn contribute to environmental and health benefits as well as reduces the domestic expense and workload on women and girls allowing time for education and productivity.

In its preparatory phase, the PRE-LEAP-RE defined multi-annual road maps and the GV1 project answer 3 of them: Smart stand-alone systems (N°3), Smart grid for off grid application (N°4), and Processes and appliances for productive uses (N°5). It also addresses climate resilience, and developing capacities at the individual and institutional levels to engage modular developments and to adapt to further changes.

This GV1 project is built jointly by European and African partners from academia, public institutions, community-based organizations (CBOs) and private partners already involved in the EARS domain and experienced in Euro-African partnership. The partners have solid and complementary experience in the region and geothermal R&D. The project follows the concept *Geothermal Village* elaborated with P. Omenda (2014) applied in the *Geopower Africa Project* (2013-2017) supported by USAID and US academies, and the recent IRENA survey. As a result, civil society organizations were created, specialized SMEs mobilized and sustained partnership developed with specialized public institutions now part of this project.

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1. Introduction

Geothermal is a flexible, full-time energy source, that allows to answer local needs and serve surroundings through energy and water networks. With the objective to introduce stand-alone electric and thermal energy an African-European R&D group was built (see participants above) aiming to provide template case-studies adapting geothermal energy resource and off-grid systems to community needs in Africa (in four selected countries representative of the diversity of situations encountered : Ethiopia, Kenya, Djibouti, Rwanda)

After field studies already engaged, sites with different thermal and socio-economic characteristics will be selected, developing for each a suitable energy plan. We aim to keep the technology level appropriate to local operation, maintenance and replication, which furthers the long-term objective of capacity building, economic and social welfare, encouraging young educated people to stay on their homeland.

These systems are conceived to supply fresh water and supplant oil and firewood which, in addition to environmental and health benefits, reduces the domestic expense and workload on women and girls allowing time for education and productivity.

This project directly addresses most if not all objectives and roadmaps of sustainable development including access to water and clean energy, climate resilience, developing capacities at individual and institutional levels to engage modular developments and to adapt to further changes, through smart grid, off grid, stand-alone systems and processes and appliances for productive uses.

2. Background, concept, and ambition

Africa - in particular all along the East African Rift System (EARS, Figure 1) and the Cameroon line - has geothermal resources of high value, shallow volcano-tectonic related (Omenda et al 2016, Gardo and Varet 2018, Rutagarama and Varet 2018).

Kenya now relies on large-size geothermal plants to ensure its electric baseload. Nevertheless, the resource – even if exceptional with steam available at the surface (Figure 2) - is essentially untapped, particularly in the remote and arid areas where the societal needs are highest.

In these areas, the energy and water issue is essentially handled by women and girls (Figure 3). Geothermal resources are known but only tapped through artisanal devices, mainly by steam condensation (Gardo & Varet, 2020 & Figure 4) This due largely to a lack of reference (demonstration) projects when relatively inexpensive boreholes can tap quite hot fluids (150°C), sufficient for electricity and many domestic, agricultural and industrial processes.

R&D (producing know-how) is required to implement at the local organization level, African solutions as the nature of the resource and of the energy demand significantly differs from elsewhere (Varet et al. 2014, Onyango and Varet 2018).

The *Geothermal Village* concept is illustrated in Figure 5. Geothermal fluid obtained from moderate-depth boreholes is used first for electricity (through ORC solutions) then in a cascade of increasingly lower temperature for direct uses (DU) such as drying crops/fish/meat, cooking and baking, fish farms and greenhouses, pasteurizing (dairy), pottery and brick kilns, timber,

bathing and washing, supply drinking water, and even provide cooling and freezing, including eco-tourism based on hot-springs resorts run by the local population.

Figure 1: Map showing the EARS (East African Rift System) along which the geothermal resource is located. Geothermal sites are found along active faults (in red) and active volcanic systems (yellow).

Map from Calais (2016) showing the plate motions (in mmm/y) within the African continent, which govern the active geothermal systems found all along the different branches of the EARS, from Malawi to Afar.

All along these geodynamic structures, there are places for local geothermal project allowing for cascade use of the energy and of the water produced by relatively shallow and therefore rather economic systems.

Figure 2.: Steam vents along a fault affecting basaltic rocks in central Afar (Ethiopia), a kind of manifestation that is quite frequent along the East African Rift Valley. A shallow geothermal resource presently essentially untapped (Photo J.Varet).

Figure 3: In the local communities living along the EARS, dominantly pastoralist, the energy and water issue is essentially placed on the shoulders of women and girls. Meaning that the social approach should be based on gender.

Figure 4: All along the EARV, various kinds of artisanal devices are traditionally used to tap the geothermal steam at the surface for domestic uses, mainly liquid water production answering human and herds needs (upper photo: EraBoru, lower photo Elidaar, Afar Regional State, Ethiopia (Photos J.Varet).

Figure 5: Scheme of the geothermal village concept with production of geothermal fluids from shallow depths intersecting feeding geological structures of the surface manifestations, and cascade use with electricity and cascade direct uses (Varet et al., 2014). The geothermal resource needs appropriate geoscientific solutions for a precise 3D mapping of the “plumbing system” of the fluids, whereas the anthropological study of the social demand allow to determine the best-suited kind of cascade uses to be implemented through the most adapted technological solutions.

First investigations (Mariita et al. 2016) show that hundreds of sites along the EARS have geothermal resources appropriate for such developments, each installation allowing modular expansion according to needs.

Based on appropriate interdisciplinary research, the present project will allow to develop a few relevant systems, adapted to the specific socio-economic needs of the local community, at an appropriate technology level. It requires geoscientific and social sciences research, the development of appropriate technologies, engineering, and capacity building in both technologies and socio-economics (Onyango and Varet 2018).

European and African entities jointly engaged in this 3-years (2021-2023) in order to develop the conceptual, engineering and physical tools to support community-based initiatives and develop local capabilities, working through schools, universities, public and private entities, cooperatives CBOs and NGOs (Onyango and Varet, 2016). Our ambition is to create in Africa the capacities to master the whole chain of basic knowledge, technology management, social organizations and economic capabilities to ensure the maintenance, extension and replication of such community-based geothermal projects.

Varet et al 2014 elaborated the *Geothermal Village* concept and conceived the *Geopower Africa Project* (2013-2017) supported by USAID in Ethiopia, Kenya and Tanzania¹ on the same subject; civil society organizations were created, SMEs and public research partners mobilized, and sustained partnership developed with specialized public institutions now part of this project (HHCBO, AGAP, ODDEG, EDCL among other).

Figure 6: Vote of the status and of community representatives for the Afar Geothermal Alternative Power Company (AGAP) at Ab’Ala (Afar regional state, Ethiopia). Photo J.Varet, January 2015.

3. Methodology and work plan

3.1. A two-step approach

The first step is identifying sites, characterizing them, and arriving at a generic energy-system plan. All these have technical and social elements. The second step is site feasibility and design. The third step, for which additional support is looked for, will be the construction of demonstrator systems for which 3 suitable “Geothermal Village” sites will be selected from the EARS.

Model plans for high-enthalpy (HE) sites in the Eastern Rift and Afar, and medium-enthalpy (ME) or even low enthalpy (LE) sites in the W & S Rifts, (Omenda et al. 2016) include also variation in societal context, where the requirements of pastoral indigenous, fishing or agricultural communities imply a different use of the electricity and thermal water.

3.2. First step

The first step relies upon 3 components:

- *Geosciences* focuses on developing appropriate methods to efficiently identify and drill into the hot geothermal fluids at depths of 300 to 1000 m. : geology, geochemistry, and geophysics for high-resolution 3D models of the underground plumbing systems of the hydrothermally active, fractured areas (1 km³ models), adapted to the variety of situations encountered (a-magmatic or magmatic as shown in Figures 7A & B).

Figure 7A (left): Google map showing the limit of the Nubian plateau: on the right (West) the Nile hydrographic basin, on the left (East) the Afar depression and the Awash River basin (Ethiopia), Marginal grabens developed along the escarpment. Location of major hot-springs sites, circa 100°C (from North to South: Harbu, Shekla, Borkena and Shewa Robit) are shown in yellow. Also shown the nearest steam vents sites in the Afar depression (in red). The limit of the Amhara and Afar regions is also drawn (white dotted lines).

Figure 7B (right): Geological interpretative section of the hydrogeological system feeding the geothermal systems (respectively hot-springs and steam vents) in the marginal graben and Southern Afar volcanic ranges. Appropriate geophysical methodology are being developed to properly map in 3D the convective geothermal plumbing system to be tapped by shallow drilling for local developments.

- *Social sciences* aim to understand the traditional social organization, gender dimension including societal roles (women and girls tasked with water and energy supply Onyango and Varet, 2014; Mariita et al. 2016), traditional economies and interest in geothermal technologies, and develop the knowledge, awareness and appropriation by local communities through anthropological and sociological approaches Onyango and Varet, 2016). Strategies and models for effective communities' engagement will be explored (as illustrated in Figure 8).

Figure 8: social approach of local geothermal projects, implying all categories of members of the community, including women and girls (left), aiming (right) not only at acceptance but at real ownership (from Onyango & Varet, 2014)

- *Engineering* will identify, select and adapt ad-hoc African technologies and local engineering solutions to high temperature shallow drilling and production and handling the geothermal fluids (pipes, heat exchangers, and condensing systems) for the ORC for electricity production and direct use (DU) cascade devices (Figure 9) - in most cases furnished by a few specialized subcontracting SMEs (Figure 10) – and further match these to the needs of pastoral, fishing and agricultural communities. A comprehensive review of such system was published by Rubio-Maya et al. (2015).

Figure 9: Cascade use of geothermal energy with electricity production through ORC plant at the first level, production of cold for cooling and eventually freezing at second level, and other direct uses at the third level, including heat application and the use of the fluid itself (pisciculture, balneotherapy, SPAs, and eco-tourism).

Fig. 10: Scheme of integration of a binary plant (ORC system) for electricity production from geothermal fluids at intermediate temperatures (80° to 180°C). ENOGIA systems allow for portable production modules in the range 20 to 200kWe, a size adapted to the needs and production expected (<http://enogia.com/wp/>).

3.3. Second step

The second step will allow to establish the feasibility of the specific sites with respect to the above results. The feasibility of community-based approaches will be assessed in terms of project design, stakeholders' and communities' engagement, and medium-long term sustainability of the project, in terms of potential business model for spread the technical solution.

It will establish the social and technical knowledge to plan the demonstrators for *GV Phase 2* and related capacity building. Staff mobility, capacity building, and project management will be specifically addressed. Towards the third step, the implementation of demonstration projects, the consortium aims to obtain funding by year two, so that the demonstrator(s) can seamlessly follow this project.

3.4. A 3 years work-plan

The Work Plan is based on 3 years detailed programs, with well-defined tasks a sub-tasks assigned to each partner, always based on afro-european partnerships. The results of the R&D engaged in first year will have provided the necessary data for engaging the detailed feasibility studies on the sites selected for their relevance to the diversity of the geological and of the social situations encountered.

A joint feasibility frame will be defined and will be applied in selected sites each of the 4 countries also involving specialized technical partners depending on the DU options considered. This will be followed by definition of proper legal framework (community-based enterprise, cooperative, "société d'économie mixte", public-private partnership...), financial arrangement (stakeholders own funds, grants, soft loans...) allowing for the project's implementation, including the process of payment by consumers ensuring the sustainable management of the whole device.

Conclusions

Given the exceptional geological characteristics along the EARS, and the rising needs of the people living there - eventually increasingly affected by climate change which induces necessary social changes - time has come to really allow for geothermal development to popularise in the African continent.

After a few years of conceptual work, and attempts to develop projects allowing for geothermal energy to serve the needs of the communities on site where the resource is available near the surface, a Euro-African team was formed to develop the necessary research in order to finally establish on a few demonstration sites the *Geothermal Village* concept.

This paper not only accounts for the program now in progress but is also a call for increased partnership - through all regional partners, ARGEO, GRMT and EAGE in particular, and any other interested party – for a successful development and duplication of such locally-based sustainable, climate resilient solutions, answering the needs of local population who really deserve our attention.

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